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A composite interferon score indicates disease severity in Crohn's Disease.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We detected the presence of interferon signaling pathway activation in the blood in humans with Crohn's Disease. The pathway activation was specific despite described global silencing of interferon signaling in the myeloid compartment in human CD. A composite score comprised of IFI35, IFI16, IFITM1, BISPR and IRF9 could distinguish patients with active disease.